

Research Article

Practice of HRMS in the Building Construction

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A B S T R A C T

Human Resource Management plays a vital role in the growth and sustainability of companies and in achieving corporate goals, as HRM is related to the practices of workers and their functional roles.

The study aims to identify the importance of human resource management strategies in building construction and the practice of human resource management strategies in the building construction industry. A descriptive analytical approach was used, and the study tool was a questionnaire. 34 questionnaires were distributed to the people involved in building construction in Tilottama Municipality for the collection of the data. The RII and mean were used to analyse the data.

The result showed that 68.75% of the companies distribute wages timely to the workers. The bias between the genders was highly in contrast to the salary distribution to the employee. Only 21.88% of the construction firms used female-qualified manpower in building construction. 56.25% of the construction companies employed the employees without any contract documents signed between the two parties, which led to lower security of the job for the employees. The result also showed that 87.5% of the companies were very concerned about the insurance of their employees. Construction companies provided compensation and benefits to the workers in building construction based on the evaluation of the employee's creativity, work performance, work quality, employee behaviour, client feedback, and attendance, respectively. 62.5% of the firms were under the democratic model of leadership and were much more successful than other leadership styles.

Keywords: Strategy, Practice, Human Resources, Construction, Leadership

Introduction

The capacity to draw in, hold, and foster skilled specialists is a vital element of effective organizations. Individuals are organisation's most important resource in low-tech, work-concentrated enterprises, for example, in development work.¹

Notwithstanding, individuals likewise address the most troublesome asset for organisations to make due. Dissimilar to actual resources, individuals have their own singular requirements that should be met and quirks that should be overseen on the off chance that they are to contribute to hierarchical development and improvement. Individuals will be people who bring their own viewpoints, values, and characteristics to hierarchical life, and when overseen, these human attributes can carry extensive advantages to organisations.

At the point when labourers oversaw ineffectively, they could possibly seriously restrict hierarchical development and compromise the reasonability of a business. There are endless instances of corporate and project emergencies in the development area that have emerged as the consequence of individuals' ways of behaving, and apparently the human asset management board (HRM) can possibly dispose of more development gambles than some other administration approach.^{2,4}

The development business has been depicted as an indicator of a country's estimated monetary improvement.⁵ This is on the grounds that development projects provide the foundation expected to oversee the financial turn of events and add to net homegrown items (gross domestic products), as well as expand the expectation for the everyday comforts of the resident. The development process itself includes different exercises with individuals as an essential element in the progress of these exercises. In spite of the fact that it is actually the case that machines were created to supplant people performing development undertakings, the facts really confirm that machines can't work without help from anyone else. They should be constrained by a human to accomplish the desired outcome. In any case, the low degree of automation in the development business of agricultural nations means they must choose the option to depend vigorously on HR for their tasks.

Statement of Problems

In the development business of non-industrial nations, HR is a critical piece of venture costs. HR costs incorporate staff organisation, worker preparation, correspondence expenses, government assistance and wellbeing, and security pay. In this way, it implies that the viable human asset of the executives (HRM) will prompt an exceptionally energetic labour force, prompting high efficiency, quality improvement, and limiting cost and time overloads.⁶

HR is viewed as one of the main assets of the present organizations. The human asset of the executives is a higher priority than other serious assets in light of the fact that these individuals utilise different resources of the organisation, make intense decisions, and acknowledge objectives. To begin with, organisations should comprehend the assumptions for their workers to accomplish the ideal presentation. The acknowledgment of the assumptions for the specialists will empower the ideal way of behaving of the labourers in the organization. A portion of the ideal results of the organisation in dealing with their labour force are: skill; collaboration of labourers with chiefs; participation of labourers between them, showing the capacities of labourers; inspiration, responsibility, and fulfilment; demeanour and presence; specialist conduct. The review is vital in light of the fact that it is an endeavour to recognise HR's techniques in structure development. The review is additionally significant on the grounds that it joins HR, the executives procedures, and labourers execution in the structure development. The review results might benefit higher administration and HR executives in the development business. Where the outcomes caused them to notice ways in which labourers executed. The consequences of the review can help architects and specialists, where they will get information and data about human asset techniques and their effect on labourer execution.⁷

Objectives

To assess the practice of human resource management strategies in building construction.

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, a quantitative approach was used to collect data from the target sample group using questionnaires. This approach is used to identify and investigate what HRM strategies are used in building construction and their impact on worker performance. In this study, the researcher used quantitative data that was taken from the questionnaires and described numerically.

To describe the impact of human resource management strategies on worker performance, a quantitative research design has been used (Figure 1).

Study Area

The study area encompasses Tilottama Municipality in Nepal, situated at GPS coordinates 27.6193° N, 83.4750° E. The geographical scope of this research was confined to Tilottama Municipality, where building construction activities by Nepalese contractors were observed and analysed.

Research Flow Process

Figure I. Research Design Flow Chart

Study Population, Sample Selection, and Sample Size

The study population consisted of 58 registered construction companies operating in Tilottama Municipality. From this population, 32 companies were purposefully selected as the sampled organisations for evaluating the impact of HRM strategies on worker performance. Both quantitative and qualitative data were collected from this sample.

Nature of Data

Primary data were obtained through field visits, questionnaire surveys, key informant interviews (KII), and focus group discussions (FGD) involving participants such as consultants, contractors, and supervisors. Secondary data were gathered from various sources, like journals, books, and previous reports.

Methods of Data Collection

Data collection involved multiple methods to gather information comprehensively. The primary data collection methods included:

- **Questionnaire Survey:** Utilised to gather quantitative data from representatives and workers regarding HRM practices and worker performance.
- **Key Informant Interview (KII):** a qualitative method used to obtain in-depth insights from experienced contractors and engineers regarding research objectives.
- **Focus Group Discussion (FGD):** Engaged key stakeholders in discussions about HRM practices and their impact on worker performance.

Data Analysis and Presentation

Data analysis commenced with summarising the collected data using Microsoft Excel. The Relative Importance Index (RII) method was employed for analysis, helping rank the impact of HRM strategies. RII calculations involved weights assigned by respondents (ranging from 1 to 5) and total respondents, facilitating comparative analysis and overall

rankings of HRM strategies' impact on worker performance. The data were further presented using descriptive statistics, tables, bar charts, and pie charts to provide a clear understanding of the findings

Result and Discussion

Respondents Profile

The samples that were interviewed during the research for this thesis are the respondents to the research. These respondents were categorised into various parts to get a deeper understanding of their knowledge and backgrounds. The various terms for which the classification of the respondent was done are presented in the below section.

Respondents by Position

Out of the 32 respondents in the study area, 34.38% are engineers working at construction firms, 40.63% are contractors, and 25.00% are supervisors working at the site of the building construction of the construction company participated in the survey from the study areas. The percentage of respondents by position is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Responded by Position

Figure 3. Responded by Working Experience

Respondents by Years of Service

The sample was classified according to the working period of the respondent at the respective construction firms. This division of the sample helps us to know about the time period of the workers in that zone, their experience with the system, and their performance as it relates to the building construction. Out of the total 32 participants, 34.38% of the respondents have working experience of less than 5 years in that particular firm; 46.88% of the respondents were attached to the company for 5-8 years; 6.25% of the respondents have working experience of 9–11 years; and 12.50% have working experience of more than 11 years within their particular construction firm. The percentage of respondents with years of service is presented in Figure 3.

Respondents by Size of Company

Figure (4) shows that out of the 32 company samples (less than 5 workers, 37.50%; from 5 to less than 10 workers, 43.75%; from 10 to less than 15 workers, 9.38%; and 15 workers and more, 9.38%). This reflects the nature of

projects and companies in Tilottama Municipality, and companies employ workers according to their needs and for the project in partial employment contracts.

Mishra (2020) replied that the number of workers depends on the number of projects running during the period. It also depends on the type of construction being done. The number of workers varies depending on the residential type of building or the commercial type of building. and industrial type of building. The variety of workers needed in the industrial building is high.⁸

Respondents by Gender

After the research, it was known that the problem of gender was present in building construction. Due to the field circumstances, the maximum number of men used in the building construction was male rather than female. Out of 32 respondents, 91% were male and 9% were female. The percentage of respondents by gender is presented in Figure 5 (Fig. 5). Female employees were prioritised in the official work rather than the field work.

Figure 4. Respondent According to company size

Figure 5. Respondent by Gender

Human Resource Management Strategies used in Building Construction

HRM plays a pivotal role in the success of any project and thus helps to grow the status of any construction firm from a lower to a higher grade. Subsequently, various strategies are being implemented during the construction of the building to improve the effectiveness of the project. A project is not a success unless it is completed on time, cost-effectively, and with quality. Improvements in human resource management improve the quality of the company. As stated by Ameh and Daniel (2017), improving human resource management is critical to overall productivity and cost efficiency in the construction industry. Various HRMS were researched in the building construction area of the research area, and the following results were obtained.⁹

The Respondents Response on Timely Wages Distribution by the Company to the Employee

Among the 32 respondents, 22 respondents, i.e., 68.75% of the interviewed persons, registered that the wages by the company are on time, and 10 respondents', i.e., 31.25% of the total respondents, replied that the timely payment of the wages by the company is not on time. There were various factors that governed whether the payment of the salary to the employees was on time or not.

During keen informed, it was responded that sometimes the salary may be lately distributed by the company due to other circumstances, such as the billing and payment by the local or other authorities to the company. In such a case, the wage distribution to the employee may not be on time. According to Maskey and Mishra (2018), one of the factors contributing to higher productivity, profit, and cost reduction is that employees should be well paid. During this research timely distribution of the wages seems that

it plays an important factor to get the positive motivation to the employees.¹⁰ The percentage of timely payment of wages by the company to the employees is presented in Figure 6.

Gender Discrimination in the Company According to the Respondent

The ranking of the respondents' opinions and preferences regarding "gender discrimination in building construction" are summarised according to their preferences with the numbers in Figure 7. Among the 32 respondents, 25 relied that the company has gender discrimination at any point, whether it be in salary, time, training, or promotion, and 7 of the remaining were confident that there was no discrimination based on gender by the company. Tessema and Soeters (2016) research concluded that due to the perceived nature of work and the common notion that it is a large male-dominated industry, the Indian construction industry has inherent gender biases. Similarly, after the survey, it was found that there was discrimination based on gender between female and male workers in building construction in Tilottama Municipality.¹¹

Tiwari, P., Saxena, K. (2012), and Mishra (2020), during his reign at the construction company, no discrimination was allowed in any way for both male and female employees in their respective positions. Gender discrimination is a demotivating factor for female employees. Some of the work can be fulfilled by the woman in a wiser way than by the male employee.^{8,12}

From the respondent point of view, ranking was done for the different variables for gender discrimination. RII (Relative Importance Index) is calculated for the variables as shown in figure 8 (Figure 8).

Figure 6. Respondent preference to their timely payment of wages

The above figure (8) shows that gender discrimination for salary has the maximum RII of 0.80 and promotion has the minimum RII of 0.48. This means the gender discrimination among the construction companies is highest on the basis of salary, and the discrimination on the basis of training is the lowest among the companies.

Types of Female Manpower Recruited in the Construction Company in Building Construction

During the research, many of the respondents replied that the use of female workers is minimal compared to male

workers. Some of the official manpower was recruited from the female gender; the majority of other employees were from the male gender. Unqualified manpower at the construction site was employed by some of the companies. 53.13% replied that both qualified and unqualified manpower are used in building construction. 25.00% were qualified female workers, and unqualified female workers were in 21.88% of the researched construction company, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 7. Gender Discrimination at the building construction

Figure 8. Calculation for various variables for Gender Discrimination in building construction

Figure 9. Types of Woman Manpower used in building construction site

Security Adjustment of the Worker by the Company

Research was done on the security of the workers, which includes the contract documents, safety tools, and insurance of the workers by the company. Among all the respondents, there were many companies that did not prefer the official signed contract document. From the interviewed 32 companies, 18 companies', i.e., 56.25% of the construction company, have employed the workers on the basis of a verbal contract instead of signing the contract documents, and 14 companies', i.e., 43.75% of the company, have employed the employees with the signing of the contract documents, as shown in Fig 10. Employing the workers without any formal contract agreement may lead to mismanagement of the company. The security of the workers is the responsibility of the company.

The safety of the workers is the most inherent factor that boosts their confidence. The performance level of the worker increases with the supply of safety tools by the company to the workers.¹³ Safety at any workplace is paramount and, therefore, should be prioritised if the optimal performance of the personnel is desired. Personal protective equipment, otherwise known as PPE's, should be supplied in sufficient quantity and required quality with strict adherence to the set standards to protect the staff from work-related hazards. In the examined sample, 20 companies provide workers with adequate safety tools, but 12 companies do not provide workers with adequate safety tools.

During the interview, I was told that the company does supply adequate safety tools for every employee, but the use of the tools by the workers is minimal during their duty time. Due to a lack of training about the use and purpose of the safety tools for the workers, many of them do not likely use the tools, although the supply of the tools is done by the company.

Good health improves worker efficiency and productivity by increasing the physical and mental abilities that are necessary for economic growth and development. Today, health insurance is seen as one of the financial ones for protection for good health, assured peace of mind, no stress thinking, reducing health costs, and financial support in a state of none. During the survey, it was seen that almost all the companies were conscious of the health issues and the accidental insurance that may occur in the construction zone.^{10,13,14}

Health insurance for the workers was provided by the company as a package. Individual insurance was not possible due to the continuity of the employees from one project to the next. once the company has to access the huge economic loss after the deaths of two of the workers working at the building construction site. After that incident, the company started an insurance policy that has helped to increase the level of confidence of the employer and employees.

The survey reported that among the 32 companies, 28 have registered the insurance of their employees, but 4 have yet to do so.

Figure 10. Comparison chart between the various securities domains

The figure (Figure 11) shows that the RII value of the insurance payment has a higher value of 0.68, the supply of safety tools has a RII value of 0.63, and the contract signed has the lowest RII value of 0.53. This shows that the respondents from the construction companies rank insurance as a higher factor for the security of the workers than the safety tool supply and contract agreement.

Compensation and Benefit provided by the Construction Company to the Workers

Of the 32 respondents, 100% of the total respondents

said that the company provides certain compensation and benefits in various terms. The research was done using the indicators that the company is using to evaluate the performance of the worker. These indicators were useful to analyse employee performance. 37.50% of the total companies used creativity as the analysis tool, whereas 6.25% of the total companies used attendance and client feedback as indicators for the analysis of the performance of the worker, as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 11. Comparison chart between the various securities domains

Figure 12. Indices used for the analysis of the employee

Figure 13. RII for various aspects for analysis of employee

Figure 14. Types of leadership styles used by the construction companies

Figure 15. RII for leadership styles accompanied by the company.

The RII for the various aspects was calculated for the comparison of the indices used for the analysis of the employee. Figure 13 shows that the creativity factor has the highest value.

0.80, and the attendance has the lowest RII value of 0.45. This result shows that the analysis of the employees is done thoroughly, from the creativity factor to work performance, work quality, employee behaviour, client feedback, and attendance, respectively. Respondents in the survey believed that the benefit was distributed upon the job cleared by the employee within the desired quality and time. This needed a higher value of job motivation, creativity among the workers, and their quality of performance.

Types of Leadership Styles used in the Building Construction

Among the five types of leadership styles, the respondent was asked about the type of leadership style implied by the construction company to get the best out of the employee for the success of the project. Out of the 32 respondents, a maximum of 62.50% of the company implemented a democratic type of leadership, and a minimum 3.13% of the total respondents said that the company implemented a delegation type of leadership style in the building construction, as shown in Figure 14.

Respondents were asked to rank the leadership style preferred by the company from 1 to 5. RII was calculated for each of the selected leadership styles by the company. Based on the RII score, the preference for "Democratic" appeared to be highly important, with a RII value of 0.89, while the delegation type of leadership has the lowest RII value of 0.60. The value of the RII preference for the leadership styles is shown in the figure (Figure 15).

Conclusion

Human resource management is a significant strategy in the organisational structure, which is of greater importance in managing the workforce and internalising the values of the organisation in the employees, which would further increase the overall positivity, productivity, and profitability of the organization. Human resources are a key asset for a company because the main work flow in an organisation depends on the performance and efficiency of its employees. Hence, human resource management is vital for any organisation to keep pace with its ethos and achieve the desired goal of development without dilemmas, disputes, and conflicts. The use of human resource management strategies in building construction and their impact on the performance of employees were researched in the survey. The set of

conclusions from the research is summarised below:

The result of the study shows that the timely distribution of wages by the construction companies in Tilottama Municipality is 68.75% of the total companies.

From the calculated RII, the survey result showed that gender discrimination on a salary distribution basis was ranked first, and other variables, training, time, and promotion, were ranked subsequently from second to last in the companies registered in Tilottama Municipality Zone.

The result showed that 21.88% of the construction firms use unqualified female labour in building construction. 25.00% of the firms use qualified female manpower in building construction, and the remaining 53.13% use both qualified and unqualified female employees in building construction.

From the results surveyed, it showed that there was limited practice of the contract agreement between the construction firms and the employees. 56.25% of the company is in progress without any agreement between the employees and the company.

The result showed that 87.5% of the companies are concerned about the insurance of their employees. 62.5% of the firms provide safety tools for their employees. This ensures the mentality of the employees, which increases their performance.

The distribution of compensation and benefits was done to the employees on the basis of creativity, work performance, work quality, employee behaviour, client feedback, and attendance, respectively.

From the survey, it resulted that 62.5 % of total construction firms in Tilottama Municipality zone uses democratic leadership style. Among all the leadership styles satisfaction level of democratic leaders is high with RII value of 0.89 and other leadership styles i.e. Transformational, Autocratic, Transactional and Delegative got the RII value less than democratic leadership styles.

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References

1. Mishra AK. Assessment of human resource capacity of construction companies in Nepal. J Adv Res Jour Mass Comm. 2018;5(4):14-25.
2. Chiluwal K, Mishra AK. Impact of Performance on profitability of small hydropower projects in Nepal. International Journal of Current Research. 2018;10(1):63918-25.
3. Chiluwal K, Mishra AK. Construction practice of small hydropower projects in Nepal. International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts. 2017;5(4):1417-33.
4. Mishra AK, Singh NK. A Review on Time and Cost Issues of Infrastructure Projects. J Adv Res Const Urban Arch. 2018;3(1&2):32-46.
5. Mishra AK, Bhandari S, Jha T. Factors affecting performance and time extension of ongoing construction projects under town development fund, Nepal. J Adv Res Const Urban Arch. 2018;3(4):7-25.
6. Mishra AK, Sudarsan JS, Nithiyantham S. Assessment of time–cost model of public health buildings in Nepal. Asian Journal of Civil Engineering. 2021 Jan;22(1):13-22.
7. Bhatta AK, Shrestha SK, Mishra AK. Job satisfaction among civil engineers working in building sector in construction firms of Nepal. Journal of Advanced Research in Civil and Environmental Engineering. 2018;5(3):9-17.
8. Mishra K. Project management: theory and practice from different countries. PROJECT MANAGEMENT: THEORY AND PRACTICE FROM DIFFERENT COUNTRIES, DK International Research Foundation, Tamilnadu. 2020 May 13:345.
9. Ameh OJ, Daniel EI. Human resource management in the nigerian construction firms: Practices and challenges. Journal of Construction Business and Management. 2017 Jul 10;1(2):47-54.
10. Maskey A, Mishra AK. Labor productivity assessment of armed police force Nepal building construction projects. International Journal of Current Research. 2018;10(11):75315-24.
11. Teclmichael Tessema M, Soeters JL. Challenges and prospects of HRM in developing countries: testing the HRM–performance link in the Eritrean civil service. The international journal of human resource management. 2006 Jan 1;17(1):86-105.
12. Tiwari P, Saxena K. Human resource management practices: A comprehensive review. Pakistan business review. 2012 Jan;9(2):669-705.
13. Lama C, Sah DP, Mishra AK. Occupational hazards identification and their risk assessment during the construction of head race tunnel in middle Bhotekoshi hydroelectric project. International Journal of Research-Granthaalayah. 2019;7(3):227-48.
14. Mishra AK, Lama C, Sah DP. Effectiveness assessment of preventive and control measures of safety implementation. J Adv Res Civil Envi Engr. 2019;6(2):1-20.